

COLONIAL POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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ABSTRACT

The Russian Empire's aggressive behavior in Central Asia, the restoration of the colonial system, the policy pursued in the Fergana Valley, the complete destruction of the Kokand Khanate, the transformation of the metropolis into a source of great khomashia were highlighted

It is known that while Central Asia allowed its influence, the Zim-rival political struggle between Great Britain and Russia (the status of the Empire was proclaimed by Petr I in 1721 year) to establish political and military rule began almost 60-70 years ago, gradually slowed down at the end of the XVIII century. Since the territorial proximity, the mutual non-wretchedness of the khanates of Central Asia and even the wars against each other, the requests of the Kazakh juz to protect them from the remnants, the yayik Cossacks and especially from the OARs, the Russian military units and the armed detachments of the Kazakhs were firmly located on the lands of the Kazakhs. As a result, the last Khanate of the Kazakhs was destroyed in 1731 year. In Central Asia, his Russian Empire carried out invasion actions taking into account the situation in Europe, in particular, the policy of Great Britain towards India and Afghanistan. In the 50-ies of the XIX century,

Russian regular troops and Cossacks occupied the Mangkishlag Peninsula, which belonged to the Kheva Khanate, and the seven oasis of the Kokand Khanate, as well as the Aral Sea basin they invaded. When England conquered the Baburid empire in 1856 year and began to restore the colonial system in India, the Russian ruling circles continued to invade New Territories one after another in Central Asia. After the first unsuccessful occupation of Tashkent in 1864 year, in the spring of 1865, the Turkistan region (Administrative Center - the city of Chimkent) was formed. With this, chorism as if it had stopped the invasion movements in the region, sought to slightly soften the discontent of England, France and Germany. In fact, the Russian military Ministry was a supporter and initiator of the expontionistic goals of the Empire and the solution of its economic and social problems on account of the opportunities of the new rich colony.

However, the Ministry of foreign affairs of the Empire in Russia in the 50-60 - th years of the XIX century Noting that Europe was strongly protesting and increasingly angry, he opposed the implementation of military actions inside Central Asia. In this Hak was the minister of the Russian military at that time D.A. Milyutin wrote: "the military Ministry at some time was in a very uncomfortable situation: on the one hand it was necessary to conscientiously submit to the requirements of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, worried about the complicity of relations with England, but on the other hand, it was impossible not to admit that at the same time the military considerations and the actions of[1]

At the same time, the military minister condemned the desire of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to convince the governments of the major states that Russia "ceased to swing forward in Central Asia when it reached its natural borders", and the Imperial troops went to the invasion actions on 26 September of 1866. Under the leadership of krijanovsky, the issue of walking to Kokand was discussed, and the Russian Chancellor A.M. Gorchakov noted that he agreed with this.[2] one of the reasons for the need to carry out such a policy is the quality of the war against the Kokand Khanate of the emirate of Bukhara and the fact that the Khudayarch repeatedly asked for help from the Tsar khukum.

In fact, unlike Bukhara and Kheva, which are constantly under observation by European countries, especially Great Britain, the West did not worry much about cocaine. Taking into account this, the Russian leadership also took note of this, this agriculture, in particular, cultivation,

developed, erotic wealth was abundant, the population sought to easily occupy a large-numbered territory, in particular the Ferghana Valley. To this end, the high-ranking officials of chorism did not return from any cunning, hypocrisy and intimidation.

There is little evidence that confirms this reasoning. For example, after the occupation of Tashkent and Khujand by the Russian troops, plans were launched to complete the liquidation of the Kokand Khanate.

General - Major g, the military governor of the Turkistan region and commander-in-chief of the Turkistan troops, on the surrender to Khudoyorkhan without any military effort and its passage under the protection of Russia.M. Romanovsky made an offer in two letters, which he sent to the Khan in August - September of the year 1866.

In these letters, general Khudoyorkhan was approached not by such usual words as "Hazrati highs "or" high gentlemen", but by "high ranking". In the first letter, in part, The Chieftains of the regiments, who came to the protection of the Master, expressed satisfaction that Rustambek, Eshboth and others did not give Khan shelter. Also in the letter "quot; assessing the orders you issued at the last moment, I myself wished you good, and not evil, and we do not want to be hostile to you, although I could have been forced to do this... I hope you will take the appropriate measures yourself and I will not go away from Khujand okru GID with the troops"[3]- it is said.

In the third letter (written in response to God's letter) g.M. Romanovsky

writes: "once again to you, I want to confirm that the mighty white tsar (in the text from this-N.Q.) it is not that he is not looking for any occupation here, but only that he wants to establish peace and quiet in the countries disturbed by wars and intrigues here, and that the people of yuvvosh and mehnatsy will be able to calmly deal with the success of the country with his work, as well as the survival of trade.[4]

As the status at the end of this letter points out, the Khan apologized that the ambassador was left to consider the military holiday in Tashkent, general G.M. Romanovsky To The Godfather... ilgarigi I repeat my request: sir your armed men (dare N.Q.) let's not let it go to the right edge and let me know what you find necessary, as you are doing now,"[5]- writes.

G.copies of the letters of God and his own letters. M. Romanovsky is the general-governor of Orenburg province N. Sent to Krijanovsky. According to the regulation, this general 1866 year in December the Chancellor of the Russian Empire (practically the head of government) A.M. He sends a 17-Sheet letter to Gorchakov and informs him about the actions of God and the Emir of Bukhara.

In this letter N. Krijanovsky 20 July to the Chancellor military governor of the Turkestan region G.M. Recalling that Romanovsky wrote about the exchange of letters with the Khans of Kokand VA Bukhoro, Kokand calls the soldiers of Kokand, who are trying to get back Khodjand in the matter of describing the issues that are still being resolved to invade Namanganni as robbers.[6]

At the moment, the Military Minister (D.), who knew that the movement of

Russian troops to the Kokand side could be allowed by the order of the Russian emperor and the Chancellor officially (in writing) (because the countries of Western Europe, especially England, were sharply opposed to this). A. Milyutin), Orenburg general-Governor (N. Krijanovsky), military governor of the Turkic region (G.M. Romanovsky) and other military officials made excuses in Turkestan, in the khanates, when it was necessary to intervene in those or those situations, there was no possibility to take the appropriate command, the list.

In connection with the fact that the military minister general Krijanovsky threatened Godoyorkhan with the possible attack on Kokand and Namanganga, as well as carried out a number of military actions, Chancellor Gorchakov noted that such actions were considered arbitrary and detrimental to the international interests of Russia. However D. As Milyutin wrote, "after explaining to Prince Gorchakov that it was not possible to ask for permission from Petersburg, although he found it necessary that the information would arrive in Petersburg in a month and general Krijanovsky would walk to Kokand, Gorchakov said that he misunderstood the letter, as an attachment to his letter: the result of what happened at such a distance,[7] although he.

It is worth mentioning that such a position was manifested not only in relation to the Kokand Khanate, but also in relation to Bukhara and Kheva, in the Kokand Khanate, where the leaders of the Garchan Empire proposed on 26 September 1866 about the policy in Central Asia," the Ilgar is committed to the program, that is, not to prevent our invasions kengaytirishga and not.

M.G.Chernyaev, G.M. Romanovsky, N. Although some of the actions made by krijanovsky and other ranking military colonialists were interpreted as arbitrary (only Chernyaev was dismissed from his post after not conquering the two marotaba Jizzah), on 26 November 1866, general Krijanovsky was transferred to the 3-Level Order of the Saint, gen g g.M. Romanovsky was awarded the title of nobleman of the emperor, graf Varonsov general - Major.

Without abandoning plans to conquer Kokand and other cities in the Fergana Valley, the colonialists forced Khudayorkhan not to act against the Russian troops, taking into account the political situation in Europe and the

invasion of England into Afghanistan, led the march towards Bukhara and Kheva. But from an economic point of view, the fact that the Fergana Valley can be a very valuable prey for Russia is relatively soon general M.D. Led to the complete destruction of the Kokand Khanate by the army under the command of Skobelev.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the Russian emperor received a huge source of Homelands for his industry, a place of settlement of thousands of Russian crestices and an area of 120 thousand square kilometers, which occupies an area of almost 3.5 million laborious, highly cultured monsoon population.

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